

Estimating Number of HIV Patients (Country Wise) Using Data Mining Tool

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Abstract--In the context of the health care system, Health problems are enormous in this present scenario especially, HIV is caused because of changed lifestyle or less awareness about our surrounding's and non-exercising condition. The data mining area included the prediction and identification of abnormality and find out the useful pattern for future analysis and its risk rate in these domains by using some algorithms and classification techniques. Today the health industry holds hidden information essential for decision-making. We Estimate the No of HIV affected persons in different Countries

Keywords — Weka, HIV, Data mining, attributes, algorithms, accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION:

The healthcare industry is generally having huge, vast and variety of information, but mining that much information manually is unfortunately time consuming and also the data that are not mined entirely which is required for discovering hidden patterns & effective decision making. Discovery of hidden patterns and relationships are the key feature for predicting the future, often this feature goes unexploited. Using clinical profiles together with country, count, WHO reports and it predict the likelihood of Estimating HIV patients [6].

II. DESCRIPTION

HIV describes a number of situations that have an effect on your body and cause death if the necessary treatment is not done. Diseases under the HIV include Pneumocystis pneumonia, such as coronary artery disease; heart rhythm problems (arrhythmias); and you're born with, among others. The signs and symptoms can be specific for each women and men as same. As an instance, are much more likely to have chest pain; much more likely to supply other signs and oxygen depletion may cause respiratory symptoms along facet chest pain, together with short breathe, nausea and excessive fatigue. "HIV" generally refers to conditions that contain some narrowed or blocked blood vessels that may result in a HIV, fever or stroke, different coronary heart situations, along with those that have an effect on your coronary heart's muscle, valves or rhythm, also are taken into consideration styles of heart ailment. You may not be identified any HIV problem till you have got a fever, chill, body pain, fatigue, Sore throat. It is critical to look at for HIV affected person. Symptoms and talk about the fact together with your physician.

Key facts

- Almost 1 million people die by the cause of HIV worldwide every year.
- The proportion of suspected HIV cases receiving a malaria diagnostic test has increased markedly since 2010, especially in the WHO African Region; this increase

in testing is mainly due to an increase in the use of rapid diagnostic tests, which has doubled since 2010 and accounted for 52% of all cases tested in 2013.

- There were an estimated 38.0 million people living with HIV at the end of 2019
- As a result of concerted international efforts to respond to HIV, coverage of services has been steadily increasing. In 2019, 68% of adults and 53% of children living with HIV globally were receiving lifelong antiretroviral therapy (ART).

Data mining

Data mining is a procedure used by groups to show raw Information into beneficial statistics through using some Software program to search for patterns in massive batches Of data, organization and teach more approximately

their customers to expand greater effective advertising and Marketing techniques, boom income and reduce prices. Statistics mining relies upon on the effective record in the warehouse, and laptop processing.

Data mining processes are used to build machine learning models that power applications including search engine technology and website recommendation programs [3].

commonly used functionalities include Data cleansing, Artificial intelligence (AI), Association rule learning, Clustering, Classification, Data analytics, Data warehousing, Machine learning, Regression.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This document is to analyse the cause of HIV disease in people by looking through different data sets and by using mining tools we are predicting the disease with more accuracy. The dataset used in this study has 7 features, one target variable, and 681 instances in which 138

suffers from HIV and 165 are healthy subjects. We are using this data sets to train a dataset and find out the accurate algorithms and its accuracy and design a suitable model for testing [5]”.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This paper is all about the process and analysis of the medical records no of patients suffering HIVs and generating pattern or identifying the pattern or behaviour of the diseases with the help of some algorithms and data mining tools. The developing tool used is Waikato Environment for knowledge Analysis (weka).

Weka

Weka is a suite of machine learning software developed at the University of Waikato, New Zealand. The program is written in Java. It contains a collection of visualization tools and algorithms for data analysis and predictive modelling coupled with graphical user interface. Weka supports several standard data mining tasks, more specifically, data pre-processing, clustering, classification, regression, visualization, and feature selection tools so that we can develop machine learning techniques and apply them to real-world data mining problems[3].

Properties of weka

- The new machine learning schemes can also be developed with this package.
- The raw data collected from the field may contain several null values and irrelevant fields.
- The data pre-processing tools provided in weka helps to cleanse the data.
- Save the pre-processed data in your local storage for applying ML algorithms.
- Next, depending on the kind of ML model that are trying to develop we can select one of the options such as Classify, Cluster, Associate etc.

- The Attributes Selection allows the automatic selection of features to create a reduced dataset.
- Under each category, WEKA provides the implementation of several algorithms. We can select an algorithm of our choice, set the desired parameters and run it on the dataset.
- Then, WEKA would give you the statistical output of the model processing.
- It provides you a visualization tool to inspect the data.[4]

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Here we're appearing 3 kind algorithm on given data set in order to create or to make out a few useful model for predicting the scope of the HIV disease for a person underneath certain situation.

Data source: Here we consider the dataset from Kaggle repository, which contains 681 instances and 7 attributes. The prediction of HIV is based on several parameters.

The data set from Kaggle repository contains the attributes of symptoms or behaviour of human body with a known target class. This data set is used as training data for the classifier. [4]

Table 1: Attributes and its values

Input Attributes	Function/ Values
Country	The list of countries
Year	The Respective years
Count	No of the Affected persons
Count_median	The Median of the Count
Count_min	The Minimum of the count
Count_max	The Maximum of the count
WHO Region	The WHO Region for the country

Algorithms

Decision Tree: Decision Tree algorithm belongs to the family of supervised learning algorithms. Unlike other supervised learning algorithms, the decision tree algorithm can be used for solving regression and classification problems too.

The goal of using a Decision Tree is to create a training model that can use to predict the class or value of the target variable by learning simple decision rules inferred from prior data (training data). In Decision Trees, for predicting a class label for a record we start from the root of the tree. We are comparing the values of the root attribute with the record's attribute. On the basis of comparison, we follow the branch corresponding to that value and jump to the next node.

```

Correctly Classified Instances      678      99.7059 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    2        0.2941 %
Gappa statistic                    0.9963
Mean absolute error                0.0000
Root mean squared error            0.0205
Relative absolute error            0.3067 %
Root relative squared error        5.6534 %
Total Number of Instances         680

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC      ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000    1.000    1.000    Eastern Mediterranean
1.000    0.004    0.990    1.000    0.995     0.993    1.000    1.000    Europe
0.994    0.000    1.000     0.994    0.997     0.996    1.000    1.000    Africa
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000    1.000    1.000    Americas
0.984    0.000    1.000     0.984    0.992     0.991    1.000    1.000    Western Pacific
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000    1.000    1.000    South-East Asia
Weighted Avg. 0.997  0.001  0.997  0.997  0.997  0.996  1.000  1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===
 a  b  c  d  e  f  -- Classified as
 80  0  0  0  0  0  | a = Eastern Mediterranean
 0 200  0  0  0  0  | b = Europe
 0  1 75  0  0  0  | c = Africa
 0  0  0 120  0  0  | d = Americas
 0  1  0  0  63  0  | e = Western Pacific
 0  0  0  0  0  60  | f = South-East Asia
    
```

Figure1: Summary for test modal using Decision Tree

OneR: OneR classifier is one of the most simple

And successful classifier algorithms for machine learning classification issues. It creates one rule for each predictor in the data, then chooses the rule with the smallest overall error to be its single rule.

```

Correctly Classified Instances      678      99.7059 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    2        0.2941 %
Gappa statistic                    0.9963
Mean absolute error                0.001
Root mean squared error            0.0313
Relative absolute error            0.3733 %
Root relative squared error        8.6332 %
Total Number of Instances         680

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC      ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000    0.003    0.976    1.000    0.988     0.986     0.996     0.976     Eastern Mediterranean
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000     1.000     1.000     Europe
0.994    0.000    1.000     0.994    0.997     0.996     0.997     0.996     Africa
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000     1.000     1.000     Americas
0.984    0.000    1.000     0.984    0.992     0.991     0.992     0.986     Western Pacific
1.000    0.000    1.000     1.000    1.000     1.000     1.000     1.000     South-East Asia
Weighted Avg. 0.997  0.000  0.997  0.997  0.997  0.997  0.996  0.996

=== Confusion Matrix ===
 a  b  c  d  e  f  -- Classified as
 80  0  0  0  0  0  | a = Eastern Mediterranean
 0 200  0  0  0  0  | b = Europe
 0  1 75  0  0  0  | c = Africa
 0  0  0 120  0  0  | d = Americas
 0  1  0  0  63  0  | e = Western Pacific
 0  0  0  0  0  60  | f = South-East Asia
    
```

Figure2: Summary for test modal using Random Tree

Random Forest: Random forest is a supervised learning algorithm. The "forest" it builds, is an ensemble of decision trees, usually trained with the “bagging” method. The general idea of the bagging method is that a combination of learning models increases the overall result. [8]

```
Correctly Classified Instances 679      99.7059 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances 1      0.1471 %
Kappa statistic 0.9991
Mean absolute error 0.0001
Root mean squared error 0.1471
Relative absolute error 37.2762 %
Root relative squared error 40.3673 %
Total Number of Instances 680

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===
 TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC  ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000  0.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  Eastern Mediterranean
1.000  0.002  0.995  1.000  0.998  0.998  1.000  1.000  Europe
1.000  0.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  Africa
1.000  0.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  Americas
0.984  0.000  1.000  0.984  0.992  0.991  1.000  0.999  Western Pacific
1.000  0.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  1.000  South-East Asia
Weighted Avg. 0.999  0.001  0.999  0.999  0.999  0.998  1.000  1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===
  a  b  c  d  e  f  <-- classified as
80  0  0  0  0  0 | a = Eastern Mediterranean
 0 200  0  0  0  0 | b = Europe
 0  0 176  0  0  0 | c = Africa
 0  0  0 120  0  0 | d = Americas
 0  1  0  0 48  0 | e = Western Pacific
 0  0  0  0  0 40 | f = South-East Asia
```

Figure3: Summary for test modal using Random Forest

Techniques	Accuracy	Time
Decision Algorithm (j48)	99.7059 %	0.036
Random Tree	100 %	2.95
OneR	99.7059%	1.19

We see that the highest accuracy for the training set is achieved Random Tree and random forest which is equal to 100%.

VI. CONCLUSION

Data mining strategies s to finding hidden understanding in a group of disorder records that could continue to be used for the analyse and expect the future conduct of the same diseases. Classification is one the statistics mining strategies used to assign a class label to set of unclassified instances.

In this paper the point of interest is on the use of special algorithms and mixtures of numerous very important attributes for This Estimation on HIV patients

by the use of data mining. Random Tree and Decision forest Tree has outperformed with a 100% accuracy by using the usage of 7 attributes.

Moreover the algorithm Random Forest having accuracy 100% as well as the performance timing of 0.07 gives a chance over the Random OneR. The algorithms are implemented with the default parameters only.

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